

Health Problems Of The Elderly and Their Impact On Their Mental Health

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Abstract:

Our current research has sought to study the most important humanitarian issues of a sacred and very important segment in all the heavenly religions and human societies, namely the elderly, and their most important health problems and diseases are known in their advanced age and old age, and what are the effects of these problems on their mental health, which is the ultimate goal of human resources in all parts of the world According to the sources available for this in the theoretical literature, starting from the divine messages and the Islamic religion, then the humanistic, social, legal and psychological theory, and the definition of this segment in general and in Iraq in particular, the research included four methodological chapters that included the definition of the research and identify its problem, importance, goals and terminology, and then the literature The most important psychological theories that explained their conditions, especially the elderly in Iraqi society, and the most important laws that were legislated for them, as well as the definition of the concept of mental health of the elderly and the effects of their health problems on them, and to clarify some of the auxiliary measures to alleviate them preventively and medically, then come to conclusions, and give the best recommendations and proposals to those who are interested in this sacred segment.

Key words: elderly, mental health, health problems.

The research problem

The problem of the current research results from seeing difficult and symbolic manifestations surrounding the elderly in most facilities of life, even within the circle of their families, especially those who develop chronic diseases, as well as many diseases, difficult symptoms and side complications associated with their old age, patients who visit hospitals and doctors ' clinics on their different, or who review health centers and medical committees to obtain medical reports, who review most official departments to complete their official and other transactions, or who stand in queues to receive their pensions or social welfare salaries on their different, or identification papers, passports, unified card and card Ration, and... And other transactions in most departments of the state, as well as the elderly, who we hear from their family members and dependents the great suffering to manage their affairs and meet the requirements of their lives, and the fatigue, confusion and waste of dignity they are subjected to in order to get what they need, which often leads to them being exposed to difficult and without want, with health, safety and dignity.

Which all this raised the researcher several questions for these manifestations, the most important of which are:

Q: What are the health problems of these elderly people And what are the psychological effects of these problems on them, And what proposals and remedies to overcome them, or reduce them as much as possible

The importance of research

Caring for the elderly, caring for them and providing services to them has occupied a large space throughout the historical stages of human societies, and the issue of caring for them has evolved depending on the changes that have occurred in the spheres of life and the change and diversity of human needs as a result of the development and progress witnessed by the modern world, which is manifested in ancient civilizations and celestial religions that have taken upon themselves to take care of the elderly and their care, due to the fact that they represent an older age group that is undergoing many physical and health changes, they need help and assistance more than other members of society, so we find that all societies, religions and throughout the ages historiography has agreed in terms of Directing care and care to them, because this further strengthens the bonds of social relations between them and their society (Mohammed, 2011, p. 44). old age and old age are stages of life that every person must go through at some time if he lives his life span, in other words, it can be said that old age is an inevitable and inevitable phenomenon, and we must be prepared for it and face it so that we live this stage of life and spend we should prepare to enter this stage and enjoy the maximum amount of sufficient physical and psychological health and a great deal of Economic independence, a high degree of adaptation and social compatibility, and thus we provide ourselves with a decent life, and for everyone to be busy with care and maintenance in the rest of life(Khalifa, 1984, p.214).

This stage is one of the most accurate stages in an individual's life. Before the end of life and the extinction of its stem in an individual, a person goes through a period in which his energies are contradictory and his production decreases, after he has had a distinctive and fruitful role in his society, he finds himself becoming less fruitful, and this feeling is usually accompanied by a feeling of hopelessness about the feasibility of continuing, and self-loathing for the debility that afflicts her. Some have expressed this by the phrase "that life is the desire to live," which means that feelings of despair and disgust may be reflected on the elderly person, seeing that others underestimate him, and it is difficult to live in their midst, and that they mock him and weaken his command, which makes his desire for life decrease, but his success in the previous stages of his life and his abundance of production during previous years enable him to hold together and feel respected (Faik, 1966, p.359). Perhaps the current era is characterized by psychological anxiety, in which the topic of happiness has made many people gasp like a mirage, and psychological comfort, tranquility and stability have become difficult to achieve, which is why mental health science, born in the twentieth century, is an attempt to return a person to his first career of physical vitality, habitual behavior, feeling happy with oneself and with others, interest in life and a sense of satisfaction, tranquility and security (Hassan and Karim, 2018, pp. 3-4).

The psychological and social stresses and the constant emotions that characterize our world today, which affect human health, both physical and psychological, as well as the transformation of civilization, changing lifestyles and exposure to external media, are among the factors that help to bring about major changes in the socio-psychological behavior of a person (Sager et al., 2018, P. 6), as a result of this, the number of mentally ill and addicted people has begun to increase day by day worldwide, despite painstaking efforts to combat these problems, mental health does not mean that a person is free from diseases, but rather social compatibility, self-compatibility, satisfaction and happiness vitality and stability, as well as This concept is narrow and limited because it depends on the state of negation or negation, and is limited to the meaning of the individual being free from symptoms of mental or psychological illness, tensions, anxiety and deviation in order to enjoy mental health (Al-jizani and Abbas, 2018, P.8).

For all this, the problems facing the elderly should be addressed and extended a helping hand to them, in order to achieve social justice, so the issue of caring for the elderly in the current era is one of the topical issues that we must draw the attention of officials and those interested in social service issues and psychological studies, in order to give them a moral value and a high status, given the services they have provided throughout their lives and their work in community institutions, and the increase in the number of elderly in recent years requires us to pay attention to them and highlight the problems they have experienced, and careful studies are necessary on what services are provided to them and

what their potential is being used, because their experience is a wealth the past and the wealth of the present, attention to them Compassion, tenderness and charity require paying for their service and drawing closer to God with righteousness, because caring for this category of parents and grandparents is a legitimate duty that we must perform, and it is a debt that we must repay, because they are Wealth, an inexhaustible treasure and countless experience (Al-Nasser, 2007, p.2).

The ability of an elderly person to get along with himself and with the society in which he lives is what is meant by the mental health of an elderly person, which leads him to enjoy a life free of crises and disorders, to be satisfied with himself and to accept himself as he accepts others. there is nothing from him that indicates social incompatibility, but he behaves reasonably, indicating emotional, emotional and mental balance under various factors and under the influence of all circumstances (Al-Rawi, 1999, p. 215). therefore, the issue of caring for these elderly people is one of the topical issues that receive attention.. Many countries in the modern era have become providing various programs of social welfare to their citizens and residents in order to achieve social justice and provide services to this category of society because this is one of the standards of advancement and renaissance of countries. this interest did not come out of thin air, but rather due to the interest in this category because it has become a clear impact on the population structure of societies, especially advanced ones, which necessitated reviewing the services provided to it and developing them in proportion to their designation in society, in some societies they represent 20% or more, such as Germany and Japan... According to the latest statistics published by newspapers about the United Nations, in 1998, 580 million people over the age of 60 lived on Earth (the world population on October 12, 1999 reached six billion people), but in 2050, it is expected that the number of these elderly people will rise to two billion out of nine billion, and the proportion of those over sixty will be more in rich countries than in developing countries (33%) compared to (21%), and in light of this continuous increase in the proportion of older people, this it will push societies to change their social structures, social welfare systems and methods, the role of official and civil institutions, families and the elderly themselves in light of new responsibilities and developments In the field of elderly care and the distribution of roles to keep up with the requirements of the times, because the problem of the elderly lies in the characteristics related to the growth that declines in old age and the situation worsens in old age, where hearing and vision decrease, as well as deterioration in many mental functions such as memory impairment and forgetfulness, in addition to sexual and mental weakness, which makes the elderly vulnerable to fear and anxiety, and then stress and a feeling of psychological pain, and the problem worsens even more if we look at the social characteristics, the social relations of the elderly are greatly reduced and limited to Old

Friends, the elderly's needs are concentrated in health care and advice his health, activities, vitality and Psychological care, which is important in providing a comfortable psychological climate for him, as well as social care to provide basic social services to secure a decent life, because the elderly

They perform a vital social function of providing guidance and expertise to their communities and families in various aspects of life, so caring for them is a necessity imposed by the nature of modern times and the religious, value and moral duty requires providing assistance, care and attention to those who have spent their lives serving the community (Al-Ahmad, 2016, pp. 8-12).

There has been a great global interest in the issue of elderly care and Health, which was represented by the fact that the United Nations declared 1999 the International Year of older persons, and the World Health Organization made this issue its theme for World Health Day, which focuses on it throughout the year.. The whole world, including the Arab world, has celebrated a focused activity on the topic of the elderly and their care, where local, regional and international seminars and conferences have been held to highlight them in order to exchange and benefit from experiences, experiences and methods in the field of addressing the issues of the elderly and providing decent medical and social care for them, and the report emphasizes the need to provide protection for the elderly in a broader sense than the issue of direction towards their treatment and the need to provide dimensions of their well-being by noting the relationship between physical, psychological, social and environmental safety, which requires broad cooperation between the state, society, the elderly themselves and their families (Al-Naim, 2001, p. 6), international conferences have confirmed and recommended about The need to provide economic privileges such as tax exemption for families caring for the elderly, promote self-reliance among the elderly, enhance the quality of life by enabling them to work and live independently for as long as possible, develop health care systems, economic and Social Security in old age, and make special efforts in protecting the dependent elderly from them by strengthening the family protection system, improving their social status, ensuring their access to basic services and ensuring financial security (Tawfik, 1980, p. 33), and thus caring for the elderly is a fundamental aspect of the assault on human wealth which became the most expensive riches All the evidence at the present time supports the fact that there is a continuous increase in the number of adults than at any time in human history, and this is not only for the growing number of adults, but also for the length of life expectancy in what is traditionally called (old age), it is very likely that it includes what is currently called the average age (al-Tai, 2018, P.8).

Research objectives:

The current research goal is to know:

1. The meaning of the concept of the elderly is idiomatic and idiomatic.
2. The most important and most important health problems of the elderly.
3. The psychological effects on the elderly of these health problems.
4. The best and most useful recommendations and suggestions, according to the conclusions, for everyone who is interested in the elderly.

Research limits:

The current research is determined by the following:

1. The theoretical aspect of the literature and theoretical frameworks on the concept of the elderly and the most important, prominent and common health problems they have and their effects on this important segment, especially in Iraq.
2. The special aspect of conclusions, recommendations and proposals that can add new and useful to the theoretical frameworks on the topic and issue of the elderly.

Search terms:

First: the elderly (The Elder):

1. The elderly is a language: he is one who is old and has lived for a long time, (a person is old and old, which is often at fifty and above the old age and without the pyramid), (a man is older, i.e. his age is older and he is older than him, i.e. older than him) (ocean dictionary, 2010, pp. 1-3).

2. The elderly by convention: it is not possible to put one specific definition of elderly people that is appropriate and useful in all cases, opinions have differed and conflicted in the definition of an elderly person, and is he who has reached a certain age, for example, or is he who looks like he is characterized by old age, And as follows:

A-the elderly according to the United Nations (1980): the United Nations report on the elderly indicated that the age (60) is the one that separates the elderly segment from the rest of the population, and this category is generally characterized by some biological, physiological, functional, emotional and psychological aspects (Khalaf, 1981, p.15).

B-the elderly according to the World Health Organization (WHO): a person who has reached the age of (60) years or more and deserves from the health system to provide affordable and high-quality care, and that these elderly people enjoy independence, self-reliance and activity as much as possible, in order to be able to continue their contribution to the development of society effectively (who Reports, 2016).

A-the elderly according to the Ministry of Labor and social affairs of Iraq (1985): everyone who has completed the(60) years of age for males and fifty-five for females and is safe from transitional and mental diseases (Ministry of Labor and social affairs of Iraq, 1985).

B-the socially, economically and biologically elderly: the socially elderly is a term recognized by a number of social and cultural factors prevailing in society.it varies from generation to generation and is characterized by abandonment in social relations.

Economically elderly: their definition is linked to the retirement age applied in societies, but it is a definition that does not take into account many cases in which a person retires for reasons other than age, without ceasing to practice various other economic activities.

Biologically elderly is a term that indicates that aging begins early in adulthood or even since childhood, and continues gradually and does not stop throughout life, so the decline in physical and mental functional abilities becomes obvious and measurable and has effects on harmonic processes (huseynat and Jebali, pp. 337-338).

C - the elderly according to the law: the retirement laws have differed in determining the legal age of retirement according to the time stages and from one society to another, it is the person who has reached the age of (63) years and has been referred to retirement", "it is every individual who has reached the retirement age i.e. (60) years and above", "it is the person who has reached the age of (65) years and retired from work" (al-Anbari, 2008, p. 7), and the retirement age varies from one society to another according to the labor laws in the world, the retirement age has been determined from (65) years and above=, but in the Arab society if the man is (60) years of age or the woman has completed (65) years of age, and either of them has at least guaranteed service based on Article sixty-five-Paragraph(A), as for Iraq, the retirement and Social Security Law has been defined for workers of advanced (large) ages who are entitled to a retirement salary if a man completes the (65) years, or if a woman completes the (60) years, they are referred to retirement and have a guaranteed service of at least (5) years (Arab Labor Organization, 1988, p.133).

W- The elderly: A category of people who are entering a stage of growth and maturity called the Third Age, which is a natural stage in human life, a state in which the decline in the physical and mental abilities and function of a person becomes obvious and its effects are reflected on the harmonic processes, a state of late maturity that follows the middle age stage and each stage is characterized by numerous changes in various social, economic and health matters, and the elderly, every person has reached an advanced age stage and the concomitant decrease in activity, abilities and physical abilities, and this is reflected in his inability to continue working, as for a person who works in state departments, leaving work according to legal regulations subject to them, including determining the age Retirement (Muhammad, 2011, p.13).

C- Thus, we can say that the age determination of the elderly or the elderly is not subject to a fixed standard in all societies and times, however, there is no purely cultural determination that rises and falls from the concept of the social culture of society, in addition, the age of fat increases with the scientific and health progress of society, but all societies are involved in determining the general framework of the age of the elderly and the occurrence of biological changes at the end of life, represented by the appearance of pyramid marks on the face, visual and hearing impairment, hair discoloration, weakness of

body cells, increased or decreased hormonal secretions, and the elderly suffering from chronic diseases such as atherosclerosis, hypertension, diabetes, as well as depression, sleep and eating disorders, etc That's another psychological problem.

Second: health problems for the Elderly (the Health Problems for the Elderly)

Health in general means that the individual enjoys full physical, mental and social well-being and not just freedom from illness or disability, otherwise health problems and diseases appear, which:

1. When an individual reaches the age of (60) or more, the stage of physical deterioration begins, such as the appearance of wrinkles, dry skin, general weakness, deterioration of digestive and nervous system functions, visual impairment, decreased mental activity, especially in remembering, imagining, perception and other changes that appear on them (Ahmed, 1976, p.357).
2. It is indicated by several symptoms such as atrophy of brain cells, osteochondrosis, mental dysfunction, sagging muscles, as well as weak muscle strength, back curvature and atherosclerosis, which makes the elderly prey to various diseases (Hoji, 2000, pp. 4-5).
3. Health problems geriatric diseases are the most dangerous for the elderly because of the weakness of the body's resistance, the severity of its impact and weakness, which reduces the chances of performing surgeries necessary for his health, and the weakness of the body in general shows diseases and physical problems such as cardiovascular diseases, osteoporosis, fractures, skin and sensory diseases, etc., and the patient may have an illusion of diseases and excessive focus on health where the simple symptom is perceived as dangerous (Al-Arabi, 2018, p. 4).
4. The health problems and diseases of the elderly may be due to the physical changes that occur to him, so they are the cause of his problems, such as heredity, profession, food and the environment are all factors that affect the organic change and health aspects of the elderly, including slow, sluggish steps, curved stature, tremor and muscle weakness, decay or weakness of sight and hearing, mental the elderly with senile diseases and the inability to afford the expenses of visiting doctors and hospitals (Sabah, 2010, p.454).

Third: psychological Health (Psychological Health):

1. According to the World Health Organization (WHO): health is a state of physical, psychological and social perfection and well-being, not just freedom from illness or disability, mental health is an integral part of this definition, public health goals and traditions can be applied and promoted in a beneficial way for heart health, infectious diseases and tobacco control (WHO report, 20009, P.22).
2. Mental health is the ability of a person to feel happy and his belief in the value of life and the formation of sincere relationships with others and return to his normal life after experiencing any trauma or psychological pressure, and it is an integral part of public

health, it is compatibility with society and not deviating from it and not contrary to it, unlike mental illness in incompatibility with society, lack of development commensurate with the stage of growth, so an adult's adherence to childhood behaviors makes him a psychopath, so mental health is the compatibility of the three conditions of the psyche (childhood, fatherhood, adulthood), because a psychologically healthy person lives in harmony and harmony with these conditions, and the disease occurs when these conditions are disturbed and one dominates the other.

3. Mental health means the ability to love and work, that is, an individual's love for himself and others to do constructive work from which he derives survival for himself and others. mental illness is hatred of oneself and others, inability to achieve and stagnation, a desire to reach death. mental health is a relatively permanent state, in which an individual is psychologically compatible (personally, emotionally and socially with himself and his environment) and feels happy with himself and with others and is able to achieve himself and exploit his abilities and potentials to the maximum extent possible and is able to face the demands of life, his personality together and his behavior be normal, and have good manners so that he lives in safety and peace (Zaidan, 2019, pp. 1-6).

Research literature and theoretical frameworks

First: the elderly in the religious perspective: Religion is the most important pillar in social life, as it represents an effective and influential force in the lives of the children of society. social systems derived from it many of their rules and worked to organize human life in accordance with the recommendations contained in all religious canons. the true Islamic religion took care of the elderly and made their place prestigious, and enacted many texts confirming their honor, appreciation and care to ensure them a safe and respectable life. it focused a lot on the psychological, social and humanitarian aspects of the elderly and made the responsibility for them common to the family, the state and society, and that caring for parents, righteousness, obedience and courtship who has the most important duties (Al-Ta'i, 2018, P. 15), and I mean Islam since This caliphate needs the safety of the mind, the health of the body and the purity of the soul. Islam is keen on health and makes it a necessary requirement for every human being, the most important of which is the elderly. Islam is a belief, thought and system represented in the book of Allah Almighty and the Sunnah of His Messenger (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) and what is stated in the Islamic heritage has given the elderly and the aging stage a distinctive care and social solidarity are only systems to alleviate the burdens of the elderly, Islam imposed Zakat, and also called for spending and helping the poor and the weak, Islam also emphasized family care and family solidarity and ensured parents, especially the elderly in the old age stage by ensuring good treatment.

From the foregoing, we can say that the Islamic Sharia and the Sunnah of the Prophet have focused their attention on the elderly, especially parents and the principle of charity to them, honoring and respecting them, which is part of the worship of Allah Almighty, Allah Almighty has eased many of the matters of worship for this age group because of its reverence and because of its disability and weakness, and Islam has urged society to appreciate the great, develop its abilities and benefit from his opinion so that he feels that he is still providing something, and Islam has provided for the elderly and made the rights of the elderly, which occupied a large degree of He stressed that knowing the right of the elderly is both an individual and social duty because the wisdom of Allah has decreed that man should move from the stage of weakness in childhood to gaining strength and enjoying it, and then this strength begins to decay little by little until it ends in more weakness, and caring for the elderly in Islam is based on pure love for parents go as far as possible, and proceeds to care for the elderly and to honor them from its framework If an elderly person does not have a family to shelter him, and sons and daughters to take care of him, and he has advanced in age, the duty of society and the state is to provide decent care for him.

Second: psychological theories about the elderly:

1. Activity theory: it assumes that the work we do to earn a living has a different perception from one person to another, work means material need for everyone, but it means other things for the elderly, so a person who loses his job due to old age or retirement often resorts to compensating for this with new goals and a new activity that provides him with a sense of identity and self.
2. .Continuity theory, which assumes that a person who is about to retire or old age in general resorts to strengthening and increasing the role he exercises.
3. The Theory of social withdrawal (disengagement Theory) indicates that aging is a matter that every person faces in his life, and at this stage a kind of mutual withdrawal between the individual and society occurs to the individual, the individual reduces the roles he exercises and society begins to abandon the individual.
4. Adjustment Theory: to reconcile the previous three theories, which indicate that the elderly person begins to reconcile with himself by prioritizing his goals depending on the new role he assumes, and the interaction is carried out through two psychological and social dimensions.

Therefore, the elderly have requirements that they need at this age stage, which are as follows:

These include food, shelter and clothing.

Addressing the health needs and the ensuing problems of difficulty of movement, mobility and physiological changes.

To address the psychological needs of his care from psychological anxiety, fear and isolation.

Meeting the social needs of the elderly in communication with his family and friends.

Integration into social life in order to avoid the feeling of distance from him (Bliss, P.4-6).

Health problems of the elderly and their effects on their mental health

The preservation and promotion of human health is a fundamental requirement for achieving economic and social development and contributing to improving the quality of human resources in life, and health is a common responsibility of all members of society (governments, institutions, associations), but people themselves have become full partners in the process of maintaining and promoting health by focusing on healthy lifestyles, enhancing their information, encouraging their healthy behaviors and moving away from harmful behaviors, thereby developing individuals' physical and mental abilities to the maximum and allowing them to have a socially successful life And economically in harmony with their environment .

The emergence of these concepts has been associated with the development of the content of health throughout history, but the World Health Organization explains it as follows:: "The state of complete physical, mental and social safety and sufficiency is not just free from illness or disability, but it will miss a very important aspect, the spiritual side, and it does not indicate that health must be perfect and integrated because this puts it at a level rarely available, however, we find that developed countries look at ideal health after a long-term goal to achieve, while what Health seeks is to achieve the positive side of programs and activities, that is, the availability of positive health energy that enables the individual and society to face problems and influences, whether physical, psychological or social without the appearance of any symptoms or signs of illness.

The health problem of the elderly represents the state of decay that affects their physical abilities, and the deterioration of the body's organ systems from carrying out their functions, the body becomes weak and loses resistance, so many symptoms appear on them that expose them to a great degree to disease and make them prey to it , such as diabetes, hypertension and hemiplegia, which is accompanied by imbalance and sensory receptors that transmit information about the movement of the body and its parts, the health status of the elderly is affected by many social factors such as the standard of living, education and the high level of Public Health, and there are several factors that affect the change organic and healthy for them, the most important of which are genetics, profession, food and the environment, they are related to The health problem of the elderly with general poor health, impaired senses and hearing .

Thus, the changes that affect the elderly are basic indicators of what affects the body systems in their exact structure due to advancing age, who are more affected than others in

other age groups by diseases and need more health care, and their diseases are not their own but affect everyone and usually begin in middle age or later and sometimes earlier and then the incidence .

The elderly also feel isolated because they have been deprived of performing many of their social roles, some of them are predisposed to accept this deprivation and easily reconcile with it and take on new roles, others are oppressed by loneliness and fall prey to feelings of self-pity, while if family care and assistance for the elderly increases, it will lead to a lack of hopelessness and frustration, perhaps one of the most important factors that increase the psychological problem of the elderly is but if he moves from one area to another, he loses friends and acquaintances and lives in a state of anxiety Deprivation is like losing an important part of his life, and he is born with a feeling of sadness and unhappiness) (Asaad, 1987, p.37).

Thus, all these psychological changes in the elderly lead to the occurrence of many psychological problems, including the so-called self-centeredness, disconnection from social life, stubbornness, rigidity of opinion, a tendency to praise and flattery, their anxiety about the future and the present, fear, which leads them to a nervous breakdown, especially after they are referred to retirement, they face difficulty in getting along with society, as well as their sense of psychological loneliness, sadness and grief after losing the love of others, their feelings of guilt resulting from past accidents and depression, especially after they have lost those who hear their complaints and meet their demands from parents and relatives (Davydov, 1986,; p.618).

But the noticeable thing is that the elderly who work after retirement age are less depressed compared to the elderly who do not work, as a result of low morale in the second category with a feeling of hopelessness and helplessness because their interruption from work causes them concern for their families and their economic situation and is accompanied by a feeling of loneliness and isolation and immersion in remembering the events of the past for their lives, activities, vitality and success in the past in their social environment, the elderly suffer from lack of psychological and emotional security in difficult situations and their inability to get along, and they need help to satisfy their psychological needs and try to communicating feelings of love and respect to them and all this is connected with the ocean The same applies to the issue of not ignoring their abilities or criticizing them and trying to help them to practice the activities and hobbies they desire, while providing them with guidance so that they can cope with their new situation in life (al-Batsh, 1998, p.4).

Because mental health basically means the extent to which an elderly person is able to get along with himself and the society in which he lives, and this leads him to enjoy a life free of crises and disorders, to be satisfied with himself and accept himself as others accept, there is nothing from him that indicates social incompatibility, but he behaves reasonably

indicating emotional, emotional and mental balance under various factors and under the influence of all circumstances (Abu al-azayem, 2012, p.1).

But the problems facing them, whether (individual or collective), (health or its psychological effects on them), prevent them from adapting to the surrounding social environment and prevent them from investing the materials available to them, and the problems increase as the elderly age, depending on their interaction in social life and the situations they are going through, in which their abilities are unable to perform some of their functions towards their families or in their social environment, as well as the difficulty of their harmony and coexistence with real life, which causes disruption or disruption in the course of their lives, they are the most vulnerable age groups to problems of all kinds, from the social point of view, because the concept of elderly people in a society is recognized by a number of cultural factors From the economic point of view, the elderly are associated with the retirement age applied in a society, taking into account many cases in which a person retires for reasons other than age and without interrupting the practice of various other economic activities, as for health and psychological, mental strength declines with age, but a certain level of verbal abilities is maintained for a longer period than physical for the changes that occur in their lives in all Perhaps the stage of preparing for death and its psychological repercussions on the elderly person and the surrounding society is the most dangerous stage, where the elderly person discovers that his life is coming to an end, passes through states of shock, denial, anger, or turns to worship for fear of the afterlife, and then the stage of acceptance, and here comes the role of faith formation for the individual to be reassured and calm (Muhammad, 2011, P.81).

Auxiliary measures to alleviate the health and psychological problems of the elderly preventively and medically

Primary health care for the elderly guarantees them a decent and safe life physically, psychologically and socially, according to the World Health Organization. in order for health care to be effective, please first agree that it must start early and be prepared before the age of (60)so that early detection of diseases, assessment of health status, taking preventive measures and qualifying the citizen to deal with his conditions when he reaches retirement age. this organized care begins with the circulation of a health card for every employee and worker who reaches the age of (40) or (50) according to the indicators of old age in any country, it includes a comprehensive examination statement to assess the health status in all aspects this examination is carried out in health centers, so the work actually begins in This examination must be repeated at the age of (55) and then at the age of sixty and then annually after that, after diagnosing the diseases of the elderly and fixing them in their health card, they are referred for free or subsidized treatment from government hospitals, as well as the preventive role of primary psychological care, as follows:

1. Cooperate with other government agencies interested in caring for the elderly by having a database of information on these services.
2. Attention to education and awareness of psychological and health in order to preserve their ability and health, through the following programs:
 - A-instructing the elderly not to isolate himself in his home or room and encouraging him to go out daily so as not to enter into the spiral of withdrawal.
 - B-encouraging the practice of sports appropriate to his health.
 - C-advice to be exposed to the sun daily because of its impact on strengthening his bones so as not to increase bone fragility and susceptibility.
 - D-advice to refrain from smoking, alcohol and taking any medications without prescribing a doctor.
 - C-description of suitable accommodation for the elderly, especially solo.
 - H-the accommodation should preferably be in a small apartment so as not to strain moving between rooms to get his needs, and it is possible to provide most of his possibilities in the accommodation room.
 - X-exclusion of non-fixed carpets that may lead to slipping and fractures of the elderly.
 - D-if the movement is specific, he recommends providing supports on which the elderly person can move inside the house or in the bathroom.
 - Y-guidance on proper food and proper cooking methods.
 - D-directing the family to the importance of psychological care for the elderly, notifying him of its importance, asking a lot about him and consulting him from time to time by finding a conscious social service.
 - G-directing the community to the importance of this psychological care for the elderly resident among them, especially if he does not have relatives to take care of it (Abu al-azayem, 2012, p. 3)
 - O-the use of important techniques to overcome poor mental health such as:

Laughter helps to secrete catecholamines and hormones that give us the feeling that we are in good shape, help us tolerate pain, help reduce anxiety, secrete natural painkillers, improve metabolism and improve muscle flexibility, so our treatment with the elderly should be looking for fun, humor and laughter because laughter is my enemy and it is a type of communication that strengthens confidence and resists anger and frustration.

The presence of distance with the elderly when we talk to him, the elderly feel that we are moving away from him and do not want to listen to him, and by touching we increase their confidence and make them feel interested in them and close to them, so when we greet the elderly we shake his hand and pass our hands over his head, we even kiss his hands and head and hold his hands when we talk to him and ask him about his condition and health and help him walk or get out of bed or when sitting.

There are scientific attempts to stop the creep of aging to humans by getting more sleep at a rate of at least (12) hours, because in the period of abundant healthy sleep, body tissues renew their cells, and practicing various cultural activities such as reading or going to the movies, a kind of change leads to the activation of their immune system, as well as a variety of healthy nutrition with scientific timings as a means of maintaining cleanliness and activity (Al-Nasser, 2007, P5).

Conclusion

The purpose of conducting this research comes from the need for humane treatment of the elderly and increasing information about their psychological, mental and social characteristics, as urged by the noble Quranic verses and hadiths that singled out this group and made the responsibility of caring for parents, righteousness, obedience and courtship of them sacred duties and work to meet their needs at the human and health level and work to provide a decent life for them and the need to benefit from their various expertise and specialties and employ them in all areas of life, and this responsibility is shared by the state, society and family, and the importance of this age group, which has not received attention and research like other age groups especially in the environment No matter how we try to clarify the causes, introductions, results and interventions in them, we remain unable and unable to provide what values the sanctity of these elderly people at this stage and what is happening in it, as the Lord of pride has sanctified it in his court of evidence, and all of us must go through it one day in the years of life, and to provide mental health components for them, it is necessary to start from some preventive measures for known, foreseeable and diagnosed problems before Or to treat existing and existing problems suffered by the elderly, such as the difficulty of adaptation and psychological compatibility with the developments of life and the required treatments and new behavioral patterns with several generations, otherwise the elderly will suffer from the necessary compatibility difficulties for a quiet life.

They are affected by general physical weakness in sensation, muscles, bones, internal physical activity, general weakness in the senses such as sight and hearing, the appearance of wrinkles, the incidence of age diseases such as diabetes mellitus, arterial pressure, loss of balance, Alzheimer's, cancers, clots and..., It is imperative that we take the necessary measures to preserve their physical and psychological well-being, it is not fulfilling and it is not fair that the elderly are neglected or left prey to this weakness, disability, illness or need, so they must be cared for and cared for, and the elderly are those who have advanced in age and reached a chronological age that cultures and scientists It gives us a better idea about a person than his chronological age, and that the concept of aging includes an increase in the body's sensitivity to concomitant diseases and a decrease in physical performance, so aging(aging) is a natural phenomenon and it is not a disease that comes for

specific reasons and leads to expected results, and that the elderly according to the in the family and society.

But human societies suffer from the problems of the elderly, even though they are an integral part of society because of their abundant giving to humanity, and the Sunnah of God Almighty in his creation that a generation will come to complete what the previous generation started so that these elderly people feel happy and blissful in the last stage of their life, and who reports indicate that the world's population is rapidly moving towards old age, for those over (60)years, and their percentage is expected to increase, especially in countries where they are subjected to some form of abuse by their families and families, as well as their countries, because one of the important categories that Zahra has dedicated her life to serving her communities, and given the problems suffered by the elderly in order to In light of these principles and rights in the Islamic Sharia, the preservation and care of the elderly is the duty of their families first, and then the state should enact laws and seek to develop legislative strategies to address their problems, and it is necessary for all concerned parties to participate in this, starting from the elderly themselves, their families and official and private institutions to distribute in all respects.

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